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QC PRACTICES: EVOLVING, DEVOLVING, OR REVOLVING AND REVOLVING?

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ABSTRACT

In a recent survey of more than 1,100 laboratories in over 100 countries, over one third of labs reported they were out-of-control every day, if not multiple times per day. Chronic flags and alerts generate alarm fatigue, just one of the many corruptions and corruptions of the QC process.

Professor Sten Westgard, MS, will discuss the key revelations found in the 2025 Westgard Global QC Survey and what they mean for laboratories. While other areas of the laboratory have evolved, QC appears to have degraded, with some practices returning to traditions from the previous century, to as far back as half a century ago.

These backward practices offer an easy opportunity to dramatically improve laboratory operations. Through tools such as analytical Sigma metrics and Westgard Sigma Rules, labs can benchmark their performance against a standard global scale, and leverage that ranking into optimizations for rules, levels, and runs. Control, calibration and reagent costs can be reduced. Time wasted on troubleshooting can be reclaimed. Significant savings are within reach of labs, if only they are willing to take a hard look at their QC habits.

Participants will learn:

- compare the weaknesses of QC practices around the world with their own operational traditions
- calculate an analytical Sigma metric
- assess the performance of diagnostic equipment on the Six Sigma scale
- design more efficient and effective QC rules using Westgard Sigma

Rules

- reduce repeats, recalibrations, reagent use for high-performing assays
- analyze the origin and practicality of the analytical Sigma metric

Keywords: global practice survey; quality control; Westgard rules; troubleshooting; repeating controls; recalibration; false rejection; error detection; trends in QC